

FREEMASONRY CLAIMS AND FACTS

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Abstract

Throughout the course of human history, a substantial number of organizations with religious or political references have appeared in a variety of locations and at a variety of times. Most of these organizations have either lost their power or vanished altogether for a variety of reasons, including having completed their mission, losing their followers, being subjected to political pressures, and being perceived as a threat by the society. or they have changed their shape. It is important to note that the continuity of these common goals and values is in line with the continuity of the

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organization. Beginning with the definition that organizations are groups of people who have come together within the framework of common goals and values, it is important to note that the continuity of the organization is in line with the continuity of these common goals and values. Nevertheless, it is possible for there to be continuity within the organizational structure if the organization has the kind of dynamism that may exist in every age of history and passes on the traditional values that it upholds to next generations. For organizational structures to remain stable throughout time, it is essential that they keep both their attachment to their origins and their dynamic nature. According to the findings of this research, "Freemasonry," also known as "Masonry," which has been a topic of interest in every era in which it has been prominent as a social reality for a variety of reasons and in every society in which it has existed, has been subjected to contentious accusations resulting from its mysterious structure, but it has been able to maintain its philosophy and organizational structure regardless of the circumstances. There will be a discussion on the fundamentals of the idea of "Freemasonry." You will not do notice that throughout our work, we incorporate various ideas with varied explanations by the prerequisites of the relevant title(s). These repetitions are the result of a methodological preference that we think should be justified using different explanations in the various places where the ideas are repeated because we believe it is vital to do so. Even though most of the ideas that Freemasonry refers to as "Secret" today have been discovered in open sources in ways that are either ethical or unethical, the institutional sensitivities of the community that is the focus of this study were taken into consideration in this investigation. The investigation was conducted by the principles of the social sciences discipline. This research has been produced from an impartial point of view, and it has accusations and responses based on scientific evidence.

Keywords: *Freemasonry, Initiation, Esotericism, Knights Templar, Symbolism, Temple*

1. Introduction: An Overview of Freemasonry

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Freemasonry is an ¹organization that is organized within a certain obedience in almost every part of the world in a way that arouses curiosity among the masses who have no concrete information about it, or as it is expressed in the own sources of Freemasonry; is a profession. Although there are a variety of perspectives and subjective sources on Freemasonry, there are also open and closed sources about how this organization, which is active in several countries throughout the globe, describes itself. It is possible to say that "Wall Builder", or "Bricklayer" is the closest equivalent that we have in our language to the term "Mason," despite the fact that several sources provide more than one definition of the term "Mason" and an explanation of its limited and wide meanings. Mason is a term that was borrowed from French and brought over to our language. In Western languages that originated in Latin, the word Mason may also be found in several forms, such as "Macon," "Franc Macon," and "Freemason." In our language, it may be construed in a variety of ways, including "Hürbani," "Mason," "Freemason," "Free Mason," and "Free Mason."² The Grand Lodge of Free and Accepted Masons of Turkey, which continues its activities as an association subject to the Laws of the Republic of Turkey and declares that it represents the traditional (Ordinary, Regular, Ordinary) understanding of Freemasonry, has made a subjective definition of Freemasonry and shared this definition on the association's corporate website: Freemasonry is a fraternal organization that consists of men who have pledged allegiance to the Grand Lodge of Free and Accepted Masons of the United States of;

The belief in God is the foundation for the esoteric and initiatory fraternity known as Freemasonry. the reign of love, tolerance, and brotherhood among people; Freemasonry, which accepts the necessity of a common humanity ideal to achieve its goal of the development of humanity in freedom, peace, justice, and tranquility, aims to promote the reign of love, tolerance, and brotherhood among people. To bring about the realization of this ideal, it adheres to the following fundamental principles: respect for human personality, service to the common good of all people,

¹Obediyan: A structure that is and implements a set of principles arising from a certain Masonic understanding and is accepted as an authority (in terms of Masonic studies) by the lodges affiliated to it.

²The terms "Free Mason" and "Free Mason" in our language are used by different associations organized under two different obediences, although they are synonymous.

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individual liberty and moral responsibility, equality of people's rights and responsibilities, and reverence for scientific inquiry.

Freemasonry is not a communal activity but rather an instruction for the individual. It ensures the largest amount of freedom of thought by communicating with its members via symbols, which it uses to express its thoughts. It never coerces, either collectively or individually, the members of the group into accepting and expressing a viewpoint or thought. Every mason handles making his own decision on what course of action to take considering the fraternity's guiding principles, using only his own intellect and conscience as guides. Freemasonry is a fraternal organization that trains its members to become more self-aware. As a result of the fact that Masons who are looking for the Truth under the guise of Freemasonry often find themselves engaged in this task in the first place, the meaning of Freemasonry might vary from person to person. As a result, the material presented on this website just scratches the surface of what Freemasonry has to offer. Every Freemason is given the opportunity to freely express themselves within this way of life. (HKMD, 2022)

Based on this definition, it can be said that freemasonry in the modern age is an ideal temple and a non-governmental organization that contributes to the evolution of individuals. Freemasonry conducts this evolution process through its own intellectual works, rituals and symbols. Even though Masonic organizations are not institutionally concerned with the religion of their members and which political ideology they adopt, they should include the individual values and acceptances of different human profiles sharing the same temple, social environment and ideal into masonic studies and meetings, or in which lodges called temples conduct their work. In buildings, they do not want the preoccupations and thought patterns of the outside world ³to come to the fore, or even to be in question. The reason for this is the concern that the diversity in the external world may damage masonic studies and fraternal relations, and the Masonic temple may turn away from its original purpose and become a means of satisfying individual material interests.

³External World: Freemasons call all environments outside of Masonic studies and affiliation (Work, family, social relations...) as the "External World".

2. Negative Approaches and Accusations Against Freemasonry

Although more than one publication about Freemasonry has been written, it is seen that the number of those who are against Freemasonry among these publications is quite high. In every period of history, three different approaches to Freemasonry have appeared. These; They can be classified as opposites, interested and neutral. It can be said that the basic dynamics of these three approaches are "Mystery". Since people could not define and make sense of the concept of Freemasonry and could not understand the mysteries called "Masonic Secret", they turned to one of these three approaches. For the Kharijites ⁴, freemasonry can be perceived as a community of intellectual, elite and enlightened people who lead scientific developments, social and political reforms, artistic and architectural innovations, as well as its policies that drag the world into chaos , organize social and political conspiracies, start wars, and target religious life and religious masses. It can also be perceived as a dark structure that produces and shapes global capital and trade. Although this negative approach is known as an approach specific to societies with a large Muslim population, Anti-Masonic movements are seen on an individual and group scale in different geographies of the world, especially in the USA. The Government of the National Socialist Workers Party, which emerged in Germany, where the political, social and economic depression was dominant, at the end of the First World War with the Versailles Peace Treaty ⁵, became a threat to the Jews living within the borders of the country and to other groups that could pose a threat to the new social structure in the ideal of Adolf Hitler, as well as to the Freemasonry. It also imposed harsh sanctions against the members of its lodges.

In the elections held on the 31st of July 1932, the National Socialists received nearly 14 million votes, which allowed them to become the leading party. The appointment of Hitler as Chancellor was made by Hindenburg on January 30, 1933. 3 Hitler was sent congratulations in the form of a telegram from the Grand Masters of the Former Grand Lodge of Prussia. In return, Hitler expressed gratitude to them. By a statute that was passed on the 23rd of March, Hitler overthrew

⁴External: A phrase used by Masons to describe non-Masons.

⁵ The Versailles Peace Treaty is a treaty signed between the Allied Powers and Germany, which won the war after the First World War, and imposed harsh sanctions on Germany. (1919)

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the parliamentary system. The Nazi dictatorship has now been proclaimed in an official ability. It wasn't long before members of the Nazi SA and SD forces' allied police and militia started breaking into lodges whenever they pleased, seizing whatever papers they could find, and arresting anybody they suspected of being a Mason. The Symbolic Grand Lodge was the one that responded first when the situation arose. At the very end of March in 1933, he made the decision to go to sleep. Following a period of two to three days, all the authorities, most notably Grand Master Müffelmann, were taken into custody. The High Council was found to be unconscious on March 31. (Delevi, 2015, p. 36,37)

There are generally individuals and groups that come to the forefront with their religious identity in the center of the negative approach that has emerged against Freemasonry and other non-governmental organizations and even professional associations associated with Freemasonry. This includes professional associations associated with Freemasonry. Although there may be more than one justification for taking this strategy, the two most important ones are discussed below. Masonic thinking and the link of Freemasonry with Judaism both have a place for faiths, and these are the spots where they may be found.

The dimensions of this association go back to the teachings of Zionism and Kabbalah. The anti-monarchy attitude of the members of the Young Turk movement, which emerged in the last period of the Ottoman Empire and brought the Western thought system into the Ottoman borders , the ⁶Committee of Union and Progress, ⁷and the Republican cadres, which were accepted as their successors, was also effective in the development of negative attitudes towards Freemasonry in our country. Following the events of the French Revolution in 1789, people all over the globe began to have views about how the state should relate to society and how that relationship should be structured. In this new order, political systems, which could not survive by preserving the existing ones, took harsh measures against oppositional currents of thought that appeared within

⁶Young Turks: It is the name given to the enlightened youth movement, which appeared in the last period of the Ottoman Empire, and which included names such as Namik Kemal, Ziya Pasha, Ali Suavi, against the absolute monarchy.

⁷Committee of Union and Progress: It is a society set up for political purposes during the collapse of the Ottoman Empire. (1889)

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the boundaries of their dominance (pressure and censorship on media organs, dissolution of societies, unfair trials, dismissal, and exile...), intellectual groups, and the state. These measures included: pressure and censorship on media organs; dissolution of societies; dismissal and exile; etc. The bureaucracy was thrown into disarray because of this. In the part of our research that is proper for this topic, we shall discuss it in great depth.

We discussed the fact that accusations and strategies used against Freemasonry in Turkey are founded on ideological and religious tenets as their primary justification. If we continue to go into depth about these ideological and religious standards, we will come to the realization that the image that is in front of us has been formed totally based on our own subjective preconceptions. The concept of a New World Order and even Zionism can be traced back to the same origins as the assertion that Freemasonry constitutes its own distinct religious system that is distinct from all other religions, as well as the view that this system is fundamentally a sect that serves the Jewish faith. When seen from this angle, it is possible to conclude that the method in question is founded on ideas that are incompatible with one another. It is not possible to build a link between a theological system like Judaism, which has tight laws and unchanging principles, and the techniques and procedures that are followed by Freemasonry. This is because Judaism has strict rules and unchanging principles. On the other hand, the story of the construction of the Temple of Solomon, which is also a part of the studies of freemasons, plays a role in the development of this link. Freemasons have been studying this tale for centuries. It is an unquestionable truth that the symbols, which are favored based on the components of this narrative and which are positioned in the temples where masonic studies are conducted, reinforce the bond that has been built between Freemasonry and Judaism. It is not possible to say that the Temple of Solomon in Jerusalem, which is revered by all three monotheistic faiths, is a correct reference for setting up a direct tie between Judaism and Freemasonry. This is because the Temple of Solomon was built during the time of King Solomon. Because if a connection is to be made between Freemasonry and any theological system based only on this premise, then that connection must encompass each of the three monotheistic faiths. To what extent, therefore, is it possible to classify Freemasonry as a cult in the traditional sense? Now, the significance of the meaning that we give the term "Sect" cannot be

overstated. "paths followed" is the meaning of the Arabic term tariqa, which comes from the same language. Even though "Tarik" is the form that is used when referring to it in its single form, the plural form is allowed and used when referring to it in its singular form. The term "tariqa" refers to the many mystic paths that are followed within a religious system for the theory and practice of that religion; yet to be considered "tariqa," these paths must conform to the fundamental principles of the religion. For instance, the religion of Islam has more than one school of thought and path to follow. Now, it is imperative that the ideas of sect and tariq not be conflated with one another. While "sect" refers to the several schools of thought and practice (fiqhi), "tariq" is the term used to describe the mystical system that has arisen outside of membership in any of those sects. A person who follows the religion of Islam, for instance, could subscribe to the Maturidi sect in the theological framework, the Hanafi sect in the fiqh framework, and the Naqshbandi sect (Sect) in the mystical framework. These are all examples of different schools of thought within Islam. Freemasonry is not a mystical movement that can be found inside any religion system; thus, it cannot be considered a cult from this perspective. Because Freemasonry is not a structure that builds its foundations on the acceptances of any religious system and is nourished by these acceptances, we say that it does not set up its foundations on religious acceptances. If, on the other hand, we define Freemasonry as "a way that a person prefers to make sense of himself and the world, to gain a new perspective by using different intellectual tools, and to support the personal development process," then it is possible to say that Freemasonry is a cult or, in common words, a cult. Freemasonry was founded in 1717 and is still active today.

3. Concepts of God and Religion in Freemasonry

Even though it was made abundantly clear, the relationship of Freemasonry with traditional religions and God, the place where masons positioned these two concepts within the masonic thought system, and how they imagined God in their minds could not be fully understood by the societies because contradictory theses were produced one after the other. This was the case even though it was made abundantly clear. The working principles of Freemasonry, the fact that it exists as a mysterious and closed community, and the grading of its members based on the amount of time they spend in the community and the intellectual work they perform during this time all

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contribute to an increased level of curiosity regarding this community, as well as a strengthened belief in conspiracy theories and fantastic assumptions that have nothing to do with reality.

Traditional religions eventually were fragmented into several distinct schools within themselves. As time progressed, the various schools within traditional religions accused one another of being politically and religiously irreligious. When put in the context of the social and political realities of the world, the phenomenon of meeting such widespread disagreements within the confines of a single worldview is something that may be regarded normal. Because religions are structures that include the cultural codes of the cultures in which they were born, their reflections in various geographical locations will also vary. This is because religions are structures that carry the cultural codes of the societies in which they were born. For instance, although if the people of the Republic of Turkey, the Islamic Republic of Iran, and the United Arab Emirates are thought to adhere to the same religious tradition, we cannot assert that the form of Islam practiced in any of these three regions is the same. This divide varies from region to region, and it may even vary among cultures that are in the same region, or even among individuals who attend the same school. Because the breadth of a person's universe of feeling and their ability to make sense of metaphysical notions both contribute to the formation of the god that the person believes in. Based on this thesis, we can say that although Freemasonry develops and declares an institutional approach to the concepts of god and religion, the extent to which this approach is shared among masons is open to debate. This is since the spiritual world of every individual (and so, every mason) is a secret that can only be known by the individual himself.

Traditional Freemasonry, also known as Nizami, and non-traditional Freemasonry are the two primary obediances that exist in our nation (Unconventional). These two schools are schools that do not have any masonic links with each other (do not conduct any collaborative work) and do not accredit (acknowledge) each other in this respect. In other words, they do not recognise each other. The "Traditional Freemasonry Approach," the institutional roots of which were created in England, is the lens through which we find it easiest to understand and communicate the meaning of Freemasonry in the context of our work. Considering this rationale, we will also talk about the

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connection between Freemasonry and the ideas of god and religion in the framework of this discussion.

"As soon as a man steps foot in a Masonic lodge, he is thrust into a vast and varied universe of philosophical ideas. In addition to that, the intellectual level is not kept throughout this introduction. It is expected of him that he would "live" by these principles. Even before he was allowed to become a member, he was informed that "Masons are required to have a belief in God." Even though the ideas of "god" and "faith" are not articulated in sufficient detail, let's just go on. Because he was a person who had a certain view, he believed he satisfied this need, and as a result, he was allowed to enter the profession. (Sanver, 2017, p. 9)

Traditional Freemasonry accepts the existence of a divine transcendent power and shapes its principles on this acceptance. While orientations such as atheism⁸ and agnosticism⁹ are contrary to the principles of traditional freemasonry, it is not possible for an outsider who has either of these two tendencies to be accepted into a lodge being traditional freemasonry. Freemasonry recognizes God as the "Great Architect of the Universe" and refers to him in their rituals. The idea of God has been articulated in this fashion for several varied reasons throughout history. Primarily, among these justifications is the fact that Freemasonry is a society that welcomes adherents of all faiths and acknowledges that diverse cultures give God a variety of names and refer to him using a variety of concepts. In the masonic thought system, the concept of god, which is known by a variety of names according to the languages, religions, and cultures of the world, is extremely significant not only for the purpose of preserving the integrity of the organization, but also for the purpose of expressing one's conception of god. The concept of God as the "Great Architect of the Universe" is an umbrella concept that may be reconciled with the belief in God held by adherents of all world faiths. Because adherents of all world faiths have reached a consensus on the existence of a deity who managed the formation of the cosmos and the biological order. Based on this information, we can conclude that the claim that Freemasonry is a religious system independent of all religions is an untrue claim, and we can also conclude that Freemasonry is a supra-religious belief system. If the belief principles of freemasonry conflict with the belief principles of any of the religions of

⁸Atheism: It is an intellectual approach that does not believe in the existence of any transcendent power (God).

⁹Agnosticism: The belief that the existence or non-existence of God is unknowable and unprovable.

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which the members are members, and if the masons have ¹⁰to choose between the principles of the religious system they believe in and the principles of the Masonic belief, they may adopt an attitude of rejecting the other by choosing one of the two acceptances. In this case, we can say that Freemasonry has the function of transforming one's traditional world of belief. However, if the masons, who belong to one of the traditional belief systems and are included in the masonic working system, have been able to achieve an intellectual harmony between their world of belief and masonic principles, then Freemasonry cannot be accepted as an alternative or transformative of any religion. As we briefly mentioned above, there are schools within the same religious system that do not share the same belief principles. Although religious systems are structuring whose principles cannot be separated and which are founded on complete acceptance and faith, schools with distinct and contradictory assumptions have evolved throughout the course of human history. For instance, there are schools within the Islamic belief system that teach radically contradictory beliefs on the role that the will of man plays in the narrative of his life. The Jabriyya school of thought keeps that man has no control over the events that unfold in his life and that everything, from the choices he makes to the circumstances he finds himself in, is predetermined by a concept known as "Destiny," which was devised by God before the individual was even conceived. On the other hand, the Mutezile school of thought contends that man has a partial will, that he conducts all his acts with his own will, and that as a result, he is the author of his own life narrative via the decisions and deeds that he does. Both schools have interpreted the Qur'an, which is the fundamental reference and holy book of the faith of Islam, to the furthest degree that their world of feeling permits, and they have arrived at conclusions that are in direct opposition to one another. A similar sharp break was experienced when the ontological features of Jesus were explained with different theses in the Christian belief. ¹¹Based on the assumption that the religious system is based on inseparable principles, a wholesale acceptance and belief, the emergence of such drastic religious differences within the same system causes people from different schools not to accept

¹⁰What is meant in this sentence is the assumptions of Freemasonry about the relationship between the God-Universe-Man triad.

¹¹Cultural, political and theological conflicts were also effective in the division of Christianity into Eastern and Western Christianity (Catholicism and Orthodoxy).

each other as a believer in that religious system. Just as it is not possible to prioritize any of the opposing schools over the other, or to regard any of them as "non-religious" through an objective perspective, it is out of question to argue that a freemason who has adopted masonic principles leaves his traditional belief just for this reason. However, since Freemasonry is a discipline that has gradual philosophical degrees, in which the evolution process of man runs through myths, rituals and symbols, it is possible that the acceptance of its members about the relationship between God - Universe - Human triad will change and transform by completing studies at different philosophical levels. Despite all these changes and transformations, one's feeling of God will be an integrated state of the components of traditional belief and inferences gained through philosophical studies. This new feeling of god will continue to be called the "Great Architect of the Universe" for that mason. We will include the Anderson Regulation, in which the approach of Freemasonry about the concepts of god and belief is declared, in the next parts of our study.

4. Historical Development of Freemasonry

It is possible to convey the historical adventure of Freemasonry, the ancient cultures it was influenced by, and the transformation process with different methods. In this study, we will discuss the historical development of Freemasonry under two headings : "**Operative Freemasonry**" and "**Speculative Freemasonry**". Under the title of Operative Freemasonry¹², we will examine the cultural background and myths on which Freemasonry is based. Under the heading of Speculative Freemasonry¹³, we will cover the institutional formation process of today's Freemasonry. In addition to the Operative Freemasonry and Speculative Freemasonry periods, we will describe the legend of the "**Construction of the Temple of Solomon**", which is a basic narrative inspired by Freemasonry and based on its philosophy, and **the Knights Templar** organization that freemasonry is associated with, under separate headings.

5. Operative Freemasonry

¹²The period of Operative Freemasonry is also called the period of Primitive Freemasonry.

¹³The period of speculative Freemasonry is also called the period of Modern Freemasonry.

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The first section of our research consisted of us setting up that the term "mason" refers to a bricklayer (Wall builder, Masonry worker). Masonry was considered an elite profession during the Middle Ages. Masons worked primarily in the construction of temples and were granted certain privileges because of their status. These privileges included the ability to freely travel, the protection of trade secrets within the organization, and the transmission of trade secrets to carefully selected apprentices within the framework of organizational principles set up by the Church or political authority. These advantages gave to operative masonry are comparable to those gave to the trade schools that were created in Rome around the eighth century BC, the Como Masters Professional Organization, and the lodges of building workers that existed in Ancient Greece.

It is common knowledge that Freemasonry originated throughout the course of time as a direct outcome of the process of development. Masons devote a lot of time and energy to researching the origins and histories of other organizations that are either remarkably like Freemasonry or may have been its forerunners. This research may take place anywhere and at any time. The use of brotherhood and collaboration, the discovery of the concept of secrecy, and the ongoing efforts with commitment to the aims have always inspired the shining of the values that were concealed in the recesses of the hearts of people throughout history. When considering the history of the Masters of Como, it is important to do so while keeping these principles in mind. There is no way to defend the notion that Freemasonry is nothing more than the whole Masonic structure. The history of architecture and the history of Freemasonry are inextricably linked to one another. Therefore, a deeper understanding of architecture will aid in gaining a greater appreciation for the evolution of Freemasonry. (John, 2016, p. 32)

At the beginning of the organizational principles, the candidate who wants to be a freemason and to be included in the lodge where the freemasons work is to take an oath that he will not share professional secrets in any way other than the lodge. Operative Freemasonry has given immense importance to the principle of secrecy to preserve the dignity of the profession and the artistic and technical knowledge of the lodgers. The Masons took these professional secrets, which they carefully guarded, from the monks who had been working in the temple building before them. Using these secrets, they built different cathedrals, castles and churches in different parts of the world.

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The characteristic features of this elite and privileged professional organization of the Middle Ages, such as being outgoing, having degrees defined as apprentice, journeyman and master, each of which contains their own professional secrets, and giving utmost importance to discreetness and solidarity, also apply to the period of speculative Freemasonry. has moved. From this point of view, we can clearly say that Operative Freemasonry expresses the formal values that shape the institutional structure of today's Freemasonry and enable philosophical studies to be conducted within the framework of systematic and common principles. In 1717, it was possible for operative masonry to turn into speculative masonry and continue their work under an institutional roof. Freemasons, who previously worked in scattered, small lodges, have continued to work under one big lodge since this date. The skeleton of today's masonic organization system has been shaped by this development.

6. Speculative Freemasonry

We spent just a little bit of time discussing the Operative Freemasonry period, which is what makes up the official structure and lodge system of Freemasonry. To make sense of the symbolic and philosophical components of modern freemasonry, it is of the utmost importance to highlight the foundations and working logic of Operative Freemasonry. This is particularly true for mason groups that preserve the traditional concept of freemasonry. It would be correct to read the process that led a professional organization, whose starting point is the operation of physical strength and technical knowledge within the framework of determined and shared principles, to replace these two factors with mental power and philosophical knowledge over time because of political and social developments in Europe. This would be correct to read because it would be correct to read the process that led a professional organization, whose starting point is the operation of physical strength and technical knowledge within the framework of determined and shared principles.

"Operative masons and speculative masons are not the same thing at all; this is a significant distinction. Operative masons are stone workers who earn their living via physical labor and are not necessarily associated with Freemasonry. They make their living by carving stone. On the other hand, Speculative Freemasons are members of the Masonic fraternity who come from a wide variety of professional backgrounds and are sometimes referred to as white collar workers.

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Examples of occupations that are historically connected with fraternity include the following: manager, doctor, police officer, and judge. Other examples are civil servant and manager. The speculative Freemasons have been since 1646, and they are connected to Elias Ashmole, who set up the Ashmole Museum in Oxford, which is today known all over the globe. Most Freemason symbols and words originate from medieval Masonic organizations; nonetheless, the terms to which they allude have highly symbolic and allegorical implications. (Blackstock, 2010, p. 9)

We can say that speculative masonry is the state of operative masonry, which is based on physical and technical characteristics, conducted with philosophical and intellectual studies. Although for masons, Freemasonry is defined as "Profession" as a sign of respect and devotion to the Operative Freemasonry period. There are significant differences in their functions. While Operative Freemasonry refers to the lodges of a single professional group (people engaged in construction work) with certain privileges, Speculative Freemasonry does not take the professional orientation of its members as a criterion for membership, and another mason who has a certain intellectual background, is respected among the society, is known for his good morals and is known for his good morals. It refers to the community that allows every outsider (non-Mason ¹⁴) proposed (referred) by the brother to enter Freemasonry if he meets certain principled conditions.

The employment of the extremely widespread ideas of "Free Mason" and "Accepted Mason" as "Free and Accepted Masons" in the time of Speculative Freemasonry, with Operative Masons who enjoy privileges such as free movement, if they are not laypeople and have not been expelled from the lodge for misconduct. It is a reference to the heterogeneous structure that developed because of the gathering of Accepted Masons, who were admitted into the lodges according to the tenor of the situation at the time. The Speculative wing of the lodges came to dominate towards the end of the 1500s because of the admission of lay people into the lodges and the weakening of traditional masonry, which was a popular profession in the past. In time, the Operative wing was eventually replaced by the Speculative wing of the lodges. This occurred because of the admission of lay people into the lodges. Masonic lodges no longer serve their original purpose of being genuine professional associations; instead, they have evolved into institutions that bring together highly

¹⁴The principles of traditional freemasonry will be discussed under the relevant heading.

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educated, intelligent, and privileged persons who are focused on their job. In particular, clergymen who were excommunicated by the church on theological grounds, intellectuals against feudalism and monarchy, intellectuals against feudalism and monarchy, literati, scientists and artists, economists, philosophers, and members of the dynasty who were excluded by the church or monarchs shared a partnership with people (Mason brothers) whom they could feel safe with and who think more or less like themselves. This partnership resulted in the establishment of the Freemasons. They have come in droves to these lodges to engage in intellectual labor and to be in solidarity with one another. The fact that lodges are made up of people who are highly educated and influential means that democratic and enlightenment movements, as well as intellectual and artistic productions, will carry the influence and traces of Freemasons in the years to come. This is since lodges are composed of elite and highly intelligent people. The Freemasons were able to take the lead in illustrious social movements such as the French Revolution thanks to a natural process that developed as a direct result of the circumstances of the time. Today, in the minds of those who look for "Mason's Finger" as a pejorative expression in the background of such great political and economic transformations, there is an acceptance that freemasonry is a community of people who have the power to realize social transformations, set up states, or put an end to monarchies. This idea is present in the minds of those who look for "Mason's Finger" as a negative expression in the background of such great political and economic transformations. Freemasonry, since it is a mysterious community with an intellectual and socio-economic level that is above the average of the society, attracted the attention of politicians as well as monarchs, and some power holders who existed within the political system of Europe desired to be included in this society. Freemasonry sparked a lot of interest since it was a community that had an intellectual and socio-economic level that was above the average of the society. To say that freemasonry has a hidden agenda and purpose in this sense will be answered as an accusation that is incompatible with rationality or an inference that is not based on solid foundations. This is because the claim that "Masons Rule the World" today is since the power holders are included in the lodges, but to say that freemasonry has a hidden agenda and purpose in this sense is incorrect. People with varying political leanings, socioeconomic standings, and occupational backgrounds often congregate in small communities (locals) that are not hierarchically connected to one another everywhere in the

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globe. This is a sociological fact. The fact that people who are also Freemasons take part as actors in political transformations, social movements, and financial actions during time periods in history has led to the assumption that all these processes are organized within the institutional systematic of Freemasonry. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] [Citation needed] It might be argued either way as to whether such a relationship is a logical kind of association. In addition, it should be said that in the natural flow of life, because of group psychology, each individual acts by trying to reconcile their own interests with the common interests of the group to which they belong and to which they belong. This is done because of the natural flow of life. If such a reconciliation is not achieved, the person in question will either willingly quit the group from which he is a part, be excluded from the group, or possibly be expelled from the organization. For this reason, it is essential that criticisms of the institutional identity and goals of any group be made in an objective and consistent framework, without accepting the passions and actions of some individuals belonging to that group as a product of the collective mind of the group. This is because it is essential that criticisms of the institutional identity and goals of any group be made in an objective and consistent framework.

We have shown that the year 1717 is the year when freemasonry in Europe achieved its institutional identity and that this year also marks the year that dispersed lodges were grouped under the roof of a single large lodge. The United Grand Lodge of England, also known by its acronym UGLE, was set up in England in 1717 and is still operational today. Its full name is the United Grand Lodge of England, while its abbreviation is UGLE.

The United Grand Lodge of England is the governing body of Freemasonry not just in England and Wales but also in the Channel Islands, the Isle of Man, and other areas of the United Kingdom. Goose was the one who constructed the Premiere Grand Lodge, also known as the United Grand Lodge of England, in London in the year 1717. and gridiron The gathering took place at the bar. The UGLE serves as the headquarters of an organization that has more than 7,000 lodges found all over the globe and has 175,000 members. Everyone over the age of 18 who is a man is eligible to become a member of the organization, regardless of their family history, religious affiliation, or race of preference. (UGLE, 2022)

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According to the claims made on the website of the United Great Lodge of England, this grand lodge serves as the epicenter of Speculative Traditional (Ordinary) Freemasonry. This is clear from the assertions made on the website. It should be reiterated that Masonic organizations are independent and local structures organized under national grand lodges that have authority in their own geographical area (country or state), although they have entered a mutual recognition relationship with supranational grand lodges in terms of intellectual values and principles.¹⁵

In today's world, Masonic lodges, which are generally tolerated in democratic nations such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Continental Europe, and some other nations, have, on occasion, been subjected to pressure from political and religious authorities, as well as, in certain regions of the world, the heads of the most influential non-governmental organizations in that society. Even in this century, Freemasonry has not been given the opportunity to express itself in the greatest and most unrestricted manner possible because of this reason. Freemasonry has always been considered as a danger by totalitarian and theocratic governments. As a result, attempts have been made to dismantle masonic organizations, neutralize them, and even entirely eradicate them, along with their members. Masonic organizations are legal structures that are set up within the political and legal framework of the state they are affiliated with and that are bound by laws and rules. Even though they are mentioned as the subject of a variety of conspiracy theories, we should emphasize once more that these organizations are bound by laws and rules.

The adventure of speculative Freemasonry, which began in England in the institutional sense, quickly spread all over the world. During this rapid expansion process, the travels, business connections, political connections, military connections, and cultural connections of people who were members of masonic lodges and had professions that required them to have international relations were influential. It is conceivable, in the modern world, to come across grand lodges in a broad variety of locations, from the states of the United States of America to the states that have been founded on the continents of Asia and Africa. Naturally, all these great lodges, despite

¹⁵This expression is used to show that the lodges adopting the same masonic understanding have entered masonic relations with each other and have known each other's grand lodges. An analogous situation exists for the liberal, that is, traditional and unconventional, unconventional understanding of Freemasonry.

keeping the fundamental principles of obedience to which they belong, have developed their very own interpretations of national masonry by incorporating aspects of their own local cultures into their rituals, intellectual work, and masonic relationship methods. This is done to create their own unique versions of national masonry.

7. The Legend of the Construction of Solomon's Temple

Today, although Freemasonry is a community that has assimilated modern technology, ancient and contemporary thought movements, local and global cultural components, it is possible to see the reflections of both its professional roots and its interest in esoteric teachings in temple decorations and masonic rituals. All Masonic lodges, whether traditional or liberal, are bound by a strong bond of belonging to ancient esoteric and mythological values. Although Freemasonry developed and transformed intellectually and formally with the emergence of speculative Freemasonry throughout history, the legend of the **Construction of the Temple of Solomon**, which is the historical basis of Freemasonry, is an indispensable myth that still preserves its mystery. So much so that Master Hiram¹⁶, who is accepted as the first freemason according to one view and the ideal expert mason according to another view, is the son of a widowed woman, so the masons also define themselves¹⁷ as "**The Widow's Sons**".

"In the Old Testament interpretations, we find two elements that form important parts of Masonic iconography. These are the double columns named Yakin (Jackin) and Boaz and the assignment of the master/architect Hiram, known as the widow's son, to this work.

King Solomon had Hiram brought from Tyre (Tsor -Tyre) . He was the son of a widow of the Naphtali clan. His father was a bronze worker from Tsor . Hiram came and did many works for King Solomon: He poured two bronze columns . He erected the right column and named it Yakin . He also erected the left column and named it Boaz . (18)

¹⁶Adon Hiram Abif is considered the chief bricklayer commissioned by King Solomon for the Construction of Solomon's Temple.

¹⁷It is also believed that this definition comes from the Cult of Isis Osiris in Ancient Egypt.

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Masonic legends talk more about Hiram than biblical accounts. Craft mythology calls him Hiram Abif, seeing him as a chief architect adept at geometry and mathematics. As a Master Mason, Hiram oversaw workers of over three degrees (apprentices, journeymen, and masters) working in Temple construction. Each rank of these workers had their own handshakes and secret words. These were used to decide Masonic ranks.” (Taylor, 2006, p. 37)

Legend has it that King Solomon ¹⁸wanted to build a temple in Jerusalem. Thousands of masons (masons) take part in the construction of the temple. Construction workers are divided into three groups according to their professional qualifications as master, journeyman and apprentice. Successful apprentices who qualify for the journeyman degree are given the professional secrets of that degree and these apprentices are referred to as journeymen. Those who show competence among the journeymen are selected by the experts and are promoted to master by being given the professional secrets of the master's degree. Hiram Abif, one of the masters, was trapped in a secluded corner of the temple by three masons, who demanded the secrets of his ability but were rejected because they were not considered sufficient and was killed by being shot with construction tools (ruler, square, hammer) which are still considered symbolic tools of Freemasonry today. Hiram's killers bury him on a hill and plant acacia branches on his grave. For Freemasons, even today, "Acacia" is a valuable tree that symbolizes immortality. King Solomon is enraged that construction has stopped after Hiram's murder and begins an investigation to find the murderers. One of the murderers exposed during the investigation is killed because of self-defense, and the other two murderers are caught and punished. The Temple of Solomon is the basic building that inspires the decorative structure of the Masonic lodges and is taken as a reference for keeping the building theme alive in the rituals . The seat of the Master, which is in the temple, symbolizes the throne of King Solomon.

4.1. Knights Templar

Although the view that Freemasonry accepts Hiram Abif as the first mason is common, another lesser-known view is that the first mason is Jesus, the Son of Mary. This view has appeared because

¹⁸He is considered a prophet in Islam and Hz. He is called Solomon.

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of considering today 's speculative freemasonry in a line extending to the Knights Templar organization and then to Jesus Christ.

It is plausible to assert that covert Christian groups continued to function after the crucifixion of Jesus, maybe even while he was alive. Freemasons who subscribe to the speculative school of thought, for instance, believe that Jesus was the first person to join Freemasonry. The history of this is based on the Templar Organization, which I discussed previously; at its core is a tiny Jewish community known as Essene. The history of this is based on the Templar Organization. It is said that this society, the precise identity and identity of which are unclear, was responsible for the upbringing of Jesus and desired to have the Jewish Kingdom. And once again, according to the beliefs, these secrets were kept after the death of Jesus by a tiny group in Syria that was shrouded in mystery. During the Crusades, the Templar Knights guarded this community and helped them sneak into Europe. After that, they traveled to Europe and, with the aid of the Knights Templar, set up the "Masonic Missionary." Here, they were hidden away in Scotland so that no one would find them. As a result, two separate currents appeared. One of them is called "Sons of a Widow," and it is based on Mary. The other one is called "Sufi Freemasonry," and it is based on Muhammad. (Altindal, 2006. p. 62).

There are several different assertions that may be made about the historical codes and basis of a worldwide and ancient society such as Freemasonry. There are schools that believe all these things, but within those schools there are other groups that have distinct interpretations of the historical process and get to utterly contradictory conclusions. Although there are opinions that set up an organic relationship between the Knights Templar and Freemasonry, there are also opinions that emphasize only thematic closeness due to factors such as philosophical degree names arising from the common denominators of these two communities (just as in the relationship that was set up between Freemasonry and Ancient Egypt) and knighthood titles. Even though there are opinions that set up an organic relationship between the Knights Templar and Freemasonry, there are also opinions that set up an organic relationship between the Knights

Hugh Des Payens set up the Order of the Knights Templar not long after Jerusalem, which is revered by all three monotheistic faiths, fell under the control of the Christians. The fact that this

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group's command headquarters was found on the hill that had housed the Temple of Solomon is the most crucial factor in explaining why they are known as the "Knights of the Temple."

Whether they took part in battle or not, all Templars were expected to fulfill a variety of duties inside the Sect. The benevolent organization was managed by its donors. The Grand Master was the highest-ranking member of the religion, and his deputy served directly beneath him. Then came the Commander of the Houses, the Commander of the Knights, and the Knight Brothers, followed by the Commander of the Kingdom of Jerusalem, the Commander of the City of Jerusalem, the Commander of Tripoli and Antioch, and the Commander of Jerusalem. Since only aristocrats were allowed to join, the Knights were a highly exclusive club. They donned the white garment with a crimson cross on it, which was symbolic of the sacrifice that Jesus intended to make and his desire to be a martyr. The Junior Marshal oversaw the infantry while the Turcopoliers were senior commanders. The Sergeant Brothers were members of the aristocracy and wore brown tunics with a red cross on them. The knights were battling under the Beauceant flag, which had a red cross on a backdrop of black and white in a horizontal orientation. (Archaeophilia, 2021) [Archaeophilia]

With the passage of time and the accumulation of plunder and privileges, the group of lowly warriors elevated themselves to a higher position. This organization ensured the safety of Christian pilgrims journeying from the West to the East, or more specifically to the holy sites, by supplying protection on the roads and throughout their journeys. The method of transferring money that was conducted by the knights of the temple via the pilgrims was crucial in the successful development of the financial system that is in place today. The applicants for the pilgrimage who paid the requisite amount to the organization in Europe throughout the voyage and pilgrimage were able to collect their money (after a specific deduction) at the center of the organization when they arrived in the holy land. They would not have to pay to stay at any of the organization's inns if they wanted to take a break while they were traveling. The wealth acquired by the Templars through the operation of money instruments, the acquisition of booty, and the utilization of the political privileges acquired by the political authorities, as well as the reasons such as the sect's breaking away from the fundamental principles of Christianity and the acceptance of the Church in order to enter into a different faith over the course of time, made the power holders uneasy. After the

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Islamic army had besieged Jerusalem for a period, Saladin Ayyubi, the leader of the Islamic army, struck a significant blow to the organization. Following the occurrence of this event, the unchecked growth of the Knights Templar organization that was concentrated in Europe, as well as the decision that was made jointly by the King of France Philip le Bel and the Catholic Church, were regarded as being harmful in terms of both religion and politics. As a result, a large-scale witch hunt was started against the members of the organization. In the year 1314, Jacques de Molay, also known as the grand master of the organization, was put to death, which ultimately led to the dissolution of the group. It is hypothesized that the members of the society who were still alive following this procedure were granted admission to the territories of Scotland, where they represented themselves in Masonic lodges and kept their religious principles and goals inside these lodges. The primary reason masons feel the need to hide themselves as a habit from the Operative period onward, particularly in Eastern societies, is that the concept of "Mystery," which arises from devotion to their ancient traditions, has appeared because of various speculations and accusations made by the society. This is true even though it is important to remember that Freemasonry has developed through a variety of experiences in various locations and at various times. It is possible that this may be considered "inconvenient." This community, which is accepted as a social group in the West, is visited by state protocols, takes part in national celebrations while wearing Masonic clothes, organizes public events, and where none of its members feel the need to hide themselves, is still not fully understood in societies that are not as developed as the West.

5. Fundamentals of Masonic Thought

Masons are said to have arrived at a distinct philosophical worldview by using mythology to back up the intellectual tools that they created throughout the Operative and Speculative eras. This is according to Masons. This comprehension was reached by delving into the masonic secrets as well as symbolism and esotericism to get closer to the scientific truth. The endeavors of a freemason to get an understanding of himself, the cosmos, and the divine system are necessary to find the path that leads to the illumination of scientific truth. Freemasonry is thus a process and not a formation for this same reason. To be able to run this process successfully requires having certain virtues,

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growing existing virtues, and even getting new virtues. Having some virtues makes it possible to run this process correctly.

Freemasonry is a society with a widespread presence across the globe that promotes tolerance, the uninhibited development of one's personality, brotherhood, and an overarching love for humanity based on respect for human dignity and dignity. It is founded on the principles that underpin these ideals. Freemasonry is founded on the principle that disputes and conflicts between individuals may be addressed amicably and without the need for resorting to harmful means. For this to be successful, there must first be the establishment of trusting relationships between individuals who have disparate viewpoints. Freemasonry places a significant emphasis on the individual and makes it a goal to perfect the person on a moral level. However, he did not personally set up any moral foundations, since Freemasonry holds the belief that moral standards are fluid and liable to alter at any time. (Reinalter, 2017. p. 7)

Freemasonry has been defined as a person's effort to make sense of his life and his goals in life, as well as stepping into a new world, a temple of an ideal, with his own will and demand, in order to be able to do useful works for himself, his family, his country, his Masonic brothers and humanity. For this reason, the temples where the Masonic lodges gather and conduct their work are called the ideal temple; a mason candidate¹⁹ to step into the masonic world.²⁰ Belief in a supreme creator (the Great Architect of the Universe) comes first among these criteria. No matter what type of religious belief the nominee mason may hold, he²¹ or she is expected to believe in the existence of a creator god (or gods). A person is free to live his/her religious belief as he/she wishes in his/her own conscience and in his external life, but it is essential that this belief is not brought to the forefront in lodges composed of masons who may have different beliefs, and even that no bets are made on beliefs and religions. A Masonic candidate is expected to be as devoted to universal moral principles as to belief in God, loved by his environment, not involved in any shameful crime, free from bigotry, gentle and well-educated. All these qualifications are extremely important in terms

¹⁹It is defined as an outsider who has declared a claim to be a Freemason but has not yet been reincarnated.

²⁰These criteria are valid for Traditional, that is, Ordinary Freemasonry. Liberal Freemasonry has bent some of these criteria and considered some of them completely unimportant.

²¹We will cover the details of this subject under the title of Anderson Regulations.

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of the reputation of the lodge to which the candidate will be involved, and in terms of the efficient operation of the masonic journey (the process of seeking the light of scientific truth). However, a mason candidate must be a man of full age and have the financial means and time to continue masonic studies. The traditional understanding of freemasonry does not allow women or those with a physical defect to become a freemason. The main reason for this is based on the period of operative Freemasonry. Since Freemasonry was born as a construction profession, having a physical defect that cannot fulfill this profession or being a woman due to the nature of the profession are obstacles to being included in the Masonic lodge. As we mentioned in the footnote, the understanding of liberal freemasonry stretches the assumptions that women cannot be freemasons. In our work, we take the traditional, that is, the regular understanding of freemasonry as a reference, and deal with all aspects of Freemasonry within this framework.

Masonic ideology promotes the concept of the immortality and ongoing development of the soul, as well as the interminable nature of the mason's quest for meaning. Expressions such as "He passed on to the Eternal Mashrik" or "He moved to the Eternal East" are used to refer to masons whose physical lives have end. Masons are known for their devotion to the afterlife. Considering the assertions, Freemasons adhere to the overarching premise of conviction that there is life beyond physical death. To put it another way, if we were to explain it using religious literature, they would say that they believe in God and the hereafter. Although various allegations have been made that neglect this truth, all these accusations are subjective, emotive, and without any basis. When developing a critical thesis on the belief values held by an individual or group, it is important to use the individual's or group's own words, whether written or spoken, as a foundation for the thesis. At this point, it is important to note that Freemasonry's believe in god and the afterlife may or may not align with the acceptances of conventional faiths in terms of form or belief. This is something that should be made clear.²² However, within traditional religions, the meanings attributed to these two concepts may show similarities or differences. If we accept that today's freemasonry is the representative of an understanding that introduced the Church-led Scholastic Europe to concepts such as democracy, equality, freedom, nationalism, enlightenment, and played a role in the change

²²Islam, Christianity, Judaism, Buddhism, Brahmanism, Zoroastrianism etc.

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of the social and political structure, we can say that the view of freemasonry on the trio of god-universe-human is different from traditional religions. It would be correct to emphasize the fact. In the works written against Freemasonry, the struggle of the Freemasons against ²³the domination of the Church over society is described as a struggle against religion or belief in God.

"Many European Masons who considered themselves to be "free thinkers" - therefore declaring their unbelief in divine faiths – gathered in their lodges, and these gatherings took place in the lodges itself. Masonry was a location where people who were seeking the truth outside of the churches could come together and unite, according to a statement that can be found in an article published in Mimar Sinan magazine titled "The First Periods of Freemasonry." In addition, this "seeking the truth outside of religion" faction was antagonistic toward religious practice. In addition to that, he was hostile. Because of this, the group quickly became a powerhouse, which caused the Church, and particularly the Catholic Church, to feel uneasy about its presence. (Numan, 2004. p. 128,129)

It's possible that the author of this research failed to take into account a fundamental idea that underpins the social science field, or that he used citations that failed to back up his own personal conclusions. The social sciences run on the presumption that the term "Religion," that is, "Religion" in the West, refers to the institutional structure and belief foundations of the Roman Catholic Church. This is because the social sciences were developed in the Western world. The institutional structure and belief foundations of the Roman Catholic Church are what we need to understand when the expression of religion is mentioned in any Western source. If the information in parentheses or footnotes is not given, what we need to understand is the foundations of the Roman Catholic Church's beliefs. On the basis of this logic, it ought to be admitted that not only Freemasonry but also the Protestant sect, which emerged as a reaction to the pressure of the Church within Christianity, is anti-God and anti-religion; however, this acceptance will not be an acceptance that is produced within a framework that is rational and logical in nature. As a result, we can say that the existence of freemasonry as a community opposed to monarchy and the

²³Vatican: Catholic Church (City-state) represented by the Pope and holding all kinds of political and material privileges

influence of religious authorities on society has caused supporters of monarchy and theocracy to produce conspiracy theories to strengthen the negative feeling towards freemasonry and to spread it to a large part of the society. This is because the existence of freemasonry as a community against monarchy and the influence of religious authorities on society has caused the supporters of monarchy and theocracy to produce conspiracy theories.

6. Basic Components of Freemasonry

6.1. Concepts and Objects

Freemasonry is an esoteric discipline that has built its world on concepts, objects and symbols . For Masons, symbols, objects and concepts are the basic elements that they interpret according to their world of perception and acquis. Masons think that they are on an intellectual trip that will continue this quest for meaning forever, and even though all symbols, things, and ideas convey profound meanings, they believe that they are on this journey. During the development of Freemasonry throughout history, these aspects have been shaped by drawing inspiration from various sources, including Ancient Egypt, the operational period in the Middle Ages, religious texts and myths, and even the cultural basin of the geography where the lodge was first established. Lodges all throughout the globe have their own unique ways of doing things, even though Freemasonry uses universally recognized ideas, objects, and symbols. From this vantage point, we can declare that Freemasonry is a one-of-a-kind society that exemplifies, as a byproduct of humans, the harmony that exists between the universal and the national. The "Secret," as Freemasonry refers to the temple and its contents, may be found in a variety of public sources, including descriptions of its artifacts, ideas, and symbols. Because we live in an information society, the natural process has resulted in many different sorts of information being available on the internet. However, we do not place any bets on the secrets that masons have bought by passing certain philosophical degrees because we respect the principles and values of the community, as well as the principles and values of all communities, and we do not believe that masons are in possession of these secrets. This is a scientific study in which we aim to reflect the objective inferences that arise from the

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examination of a generous part of open and closed sources. In this study, we include both negative and positive perspectives on Freemasonry because we believe it is important to supply a balanced perspective.

Freemasonry is a structure that bases the intellectual foundations of its work on the concepts of the construction profession. It also associates the symbols and concepts of this profession with speculative and esoteric data. The construction profession is the basis for the intellectual foundations of the work that Freemasonry does. The first of its kind was set up in the United States in the year 1717, and since then it has proliferated all over the globe. For instance, other members of the lodge will refer to a brother who has just joined as "raw stone." This is because the brother is yet unseasoned in the lodge. Each stonemason, irrespective of the position he holds, considers himself to be an uncut block of stone. Because the process of human growth is a process that spans to eternity, and a mason handles growing himself throughout eternity, and because a mason may better themselves by "chipping raw stone into cubes," the process of human development is a process that spans to eternity. It would be good to supply a few examples to explain this figurative term that is simple to understand. The flaws that are inherent to him and over which he has no control are comparable to the jagged corners of a block of stone that must be hacked away. It is possible for a person to have characteristics such as an uncontrolled ego, arrogance, jealousy, putting worldly interests above everything else, and greed for power because the person must confess these characteristics to himself for the evolution, which is the process of carving the raw stone, to begin with a symbolic expression. This is because the person must put worldly interests above everything else. Considered analogous to the process of chiseling squares out of rough stone via intellectual and spiritual labor is the endeavor to remove oneself of the unfavorable characteristics. Mystical groups and faiths all share certain goals but pursue them in remarkably diverse ways. For instance, in the religion of Islam, the worship known as "Fasting" is an essential worship that is performed to subdue one's inner impulses and to cultivate a compassionate attitude toward others who are in this circumstance by experiencing deprivations such as hunger and thirst. The purpose of confessing one's sins in the Christian religion is to acknowledge one's own transgressions, to feel humiliation over them, and to begin a new life by placing one's trust in God's

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grace and compassion. Within its own systems, Freemasonry employs a variety of intellectual activities (rituals), all with the goal of removing the unfavorable qualities that are associated with human beings. When a brother considers his own mortality, remembers his obligations to his family, his country, his fellow Masons, and humanity, and displays attitudes and behaviors that are considered beneficial by the universal human mind (such as cooperation, self-development, respect for nature and living things, etc.), evolution continues unabated. It is expected that he will always see himself as flawed and draw a profile that will set an example for other people. Every new mason who joins the lodge is surrounded by a white apron and white gloves, and it is aimed to convey the feelings of cleanliness and innocence.²⁴

For Masons, abstract productions are as important as concrete tools. Masonic lodges, which work with three different symbolic degrees such as apprenticeship, journeyman and master, are structures where ²⁵esoteric teachings are shared as well as symbolic rituals and intellectual studies ."*Esotericism is a belief system based on the idea that everything based on the identity of God, the Universe, and Human beings' springs from God and is a part of it. The aim is to bring these experiences together and reach a higher level of consciousness for each part having different experiences. Esotericism's method of reaching the goal is Evolution, that is, Evolvment. Evolution, that is, the Law of Evolvment, is a law that will last from eternity to eternity. At the very first moment of the beginning, which is Surud, that is, the Big Bang, the law of evolution began to work, and energy transformed into matter and created the Universe. The goal of every particle separated from God is to return to the main source from which it was separated.*" (Gener, 2019. p. 9)

The expressions in the paragraph make it clear that esotericism views the universe and man as components of the Divine System, that it is predicated on the assumption that God is the origin of absolute knowledge, and that it emphasizes that in order for man to achieve absolute knowledge,

²⁴The origin of the white apron and gloves symbolizing innocence and cleanliness is the legend that when Hiram Master, believed to have been killed by three journeymen, was buried, the expert masons wore white gloves and aprons to show that they were innocent and clean.

²⁵Although it is widely accepted that there are 33 degrees in Freemasonry, Freemasonry basically has 3 degrees: Apprentice, Journeyman and Master. The 4th and 33rd degrees are degrees of a different system of philosophical study, called the Old and Accepted Scottish Rite, which the expert masons in the lodge can pursue optionally. In time, different Rit systems were born.

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he must carry out the evolutionary process while adhering to the laws that govern this system. As was discussed in the earlier paragraph, for evolution to go ahead by the divine system, it is necessary for a person to acknowledge the negative aspects of themselves, be honest with themselves, and put in the mental effort necessary to rid themselves of these negative aspects. In this regard, Freemasonry is both a goal to be conducted and a way to approach immortality.

6.2. Contemplation

The journey to infinity begins with contemplation, which is the first step on the path. The act of a person contemplating about things such as the world, God, the nature he watches, and himself is referred to as contemplation. The reason of being in the cosmos, the purpose of life, the glory of God, good actions, evil deeds, examination, travel to the past, and goals for the future are all included in this process. On the basis that time is relative, although it is not possible to make a clear determination about how long this process will take or how long it should last, it is correct to say that contemplation is an ongoing action that extends to infinity. This is the case even though it is not possible to make a clear determination about how long this process will take. Based on the conclusions that one draws throughout the process of contemplation; the primary purpose of meditation is to force oneself into confrontation with oneself and to construct a system of self-control that one will need during the trip. For instance, if a person's environment labels them as "Unreliable," that person ought to be bothered by the label and try to rid themselves of the factors that contribute to the label during the contemplation process by deciding the factors that contribute to the characterization of themselves as unreliable. It is important for him to live his life with the understanding that activities such as contemplating what is noble and lovely and producing works that help others are behaviors that bring people closer to the divine light, just as the esoteric understanding and the traditional religious systems teach.

We can say that the Masonic system is the discipline of thinking with symbols and reinterpreting the relationship between the God-Man-Universe triad, the dynamics of the physical external world, and the spiritual world, using the perspective that is born within the framework of the meaning sets represented by the symbols. We can say this because the Masonic system has been around for

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an exceptionally long time and has been passed down from generation to generation. The interpretations of the symbols are deep and extensive enough to fill an abyss forever. These symbols may be broken down into four distinct categories: visual, aural, numerical, and behavioral. It is possible to generate an endless number of views by combining the four symbol sets with a variety of algorithms and then applying intellectual values on top of this foundation.

6.3. Tekris (Initiation, Enlightenment)

The realization of the step taken to the Masonic world within the framework of a systematic ceremony can be seen as a symbolic reflection of a tradition dating back to ancient times. As we mentioned in the first part of our study, commitment to traditional elements is of immense importance in the continuity of organizations. We can say that the references made to the achievements gained in the historical process are the steps taken to give the institutional structure a quality beyond time and space. The most important of these references, and perhaps the first image that comes to life in the minds of the parties when the subject of Freemasonry is **brought up, "The Ceremony of Initiation" is a practice on which various** manipulative discussions are still being carried out, especially since the moment it took place in the conventional media .²⁶Tekris is a word of Arabic origin and means "foundation". It is a ceremony that is the initiation and enlightenment of the candidate, called external . It is a reality that today's society has difficulty in making sense of the theatrical atmosphere of this ceremony , especially if we accept that they are exposed to manipulative information, as it has some elements from the operative Freemasonry period. The ceremony of initiation is a rite of passage in which the person who steps into Freemasonry opens a new and clean page, leaves his titles and qualifications in the external world behind, and is accepted into the lodge, the brotherhood, working at the apprentice level.

6.4. Importance of the Temple

²⁶Hidden camera footage broadcast by Kanal 7 Television broadcasting in Turkey in 1997 and allegedly belonging to a Masonic lodge in Turkey.

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Freemasons perform their masonic work and rituals in halls they gather in lodges²⁷, which they call the ideal sanctuary. These temples are special halls decorated under the physical structure of the association buildings. Although there are slight differences from country to country, all temples are the same in terms of general features because they are decorated in a way that reminds them of the Temple of Solomon. Symbolic elements that were drawn on the soil in the operative period and erased at the end of the work became indispensable for the temples, which became permanent with the speculative period. The physical atmosphere of the temple is extremely important in that masons are inspired by the past, internalize the world of symbolism and carry out their work within a certain set of rules. The temples, where the earth, light, the galactic system and the texts representing the traditional sacred values, are aligned with the construction tools, each of which has a separate set of deep meanings, rise above reason and wisdom, strength and beauty. They are constantly checked and supported by the Great Architect of the Universe.

It is possible to reach innumerable data on the visual characteristics of Masons on the internet and in documentary productions on the subject. However, the costumes of mysterious (even malicious) communities that take part in the productions that we can call fictional productions (Cinema, Serial Film) are perceived as "Mason" outfits by a large part of the society. Numerous esoteric and Initiation-based communities have arisen and perished throughout history. Perceiving and defining all these communities, which are the subject of fictional productions, as "Masonic Community" will not be compatible with reality. Sometimes, common symbolic elements or similarities in terms of organization can be found between "Masonry" and other communities. This coincidence arises from the use of common cultural basins, common universal life cycle and common historical memory of humanity. For example, there may be visual similarities (such as putting on a turban) between an Indian who professes the Hindu faith and a Muslim living in the Middle East and adopting the first-generation clothing style. Based on this similarity, we cannot say that these two individuals are in a religious closeness.

²⁷The concepts of Lodge and Temple are concepts that are often confused among the people. While the lodge refers to a certain number of mason community, the physical structures (Halls) that are incorrectly referred to as "Loca" are called "The Temple".

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Today, the basis of Masonic clothing is a black suit, black tie or bow tie, white gloves and apron. The members of the lodge also have variants and accessories that express their duties in the temple and their rank in the masonic life. For example, there are factors that will make a visual difference, such as the degree of masonic life shaping the visual features of the mason apron, the carrying of symbols called regalye jewelery expressing the duty in the lodge, the wearing of the badge with the special emblem of the lodge and the medals earned over time. Although Freemasonry has created its modern style of clothing with references to the Operative Freemasonry Period and the Legend of the Construction of the Temple of Solomon, there are also formations in some geographies that prefer to dress differently from the general and define themselves as Masonic.²⁸

6.5. Organizational Structure

Freemasonry works within an organizational structure that extends from the past to the present. Although the organizational structure has undergone minor transformations over time, it is based on the relationship between Master - Journeyman - Apprentice based on members, and Lodge - Valley - Grand Lodge (principles of obedience to which the Grand Lodge is connected) based on lodges. The working system in the lodge is formed by the coming together of masons of different degrees. The apprentice-level members who have just joined the community, the members who are promoted to the level of journeyman by completing one year in the lodge and fulfilling the necessary assignments, spent more than two years in the lodge, performed the necessary studies and took care not to be absent, members at the master (master) level and the Great Leader who presided over the lodge. The Master²⁹ is the components of this system. As said in open sources, some of the master-level masons have certain duties and powers to conduct the works in a systematic way. These duties and powers are valid for a certain period and are assumed alternately by other members of the lodge. Ustad-ı Muhterem, like the officers he worked with, will transfer his duty and title when his term of office expires. Lodges are attached to the grand lodge, but they are within the responsibility area of a valley determined according to their geographical area. For example, a lodge running in Central Anatolia is probably connected to the Ankara Valley. This

²⁸Established in New York in 1870, the group working under the Shrine Riti focuses on Islamic and Ottoman motifs.

²⁹The Great Master is also known as the Reverend Master or the Reverend Master.

system is the system preferred by the Grand Lodge to keep the order within the organizational structure. Commercial organizations and public institutions running in the private sector also conduct their activities in a more systematic way through "Regional Directorates". The Grand Lodge has all kinds of authority over the valleys connected to it and the lodges that these valleys have and uses these powers through the relevant units it creates within the lodge. The budget of the association is provided by membership fees, membership entrance fees and economic enterprise incomes. While this budget is used for the provision of services for the members to conduct their work in a complete manner and for the expenses of the association's buildings, Masonic associations, like any other association, can also conduct charity activities (for example, giving scholarships).

6.6. Symbols and Tools

We have said that Freemasonry is the discipline of thinking with symbols. We can say that symbols are the reflections of the world of masonic ideas in the physical world. A Masonic life without symbols, objects and ideas is unthinkable. Washington DC, the capital of the United States, is full of Masonic architecture and symbols. The main reason for this is that the founding cadres of the USA are freemasons. It cannot be said that the affinity in principle between the Declaration ³⁰of Independence and the Anderson Ordinance, which we will discuss in the next section, is a coincidence.

Although there are symbols associated with Freemasonry but not related, there are symbols that only evoke Freemasonry when seen and are used extensively by masons. These; It can be listed as square and compass placed on top of each other, with or without the letter "G" in the middle, eye in the pyramid, checkered ground, six-pointed star, triangle. It should be noted that the number of symbols contained in the Masonic world is not limited to the ones given here, and the world of symbols is not just visual symbols. Behavioral, auditory and visual symbols are components that work in harmony with each other. Although the meanings attributed to the symbols bear the traces of the Ancient Egypt, Jerusalem and Medieval Europe periods, every mason can make sense of all

³⁰The American Declaration of Independence is the document in which the thirteen colonies declared their independence from Britain. Confirmed on July 2, 1776, proclaimed on July 4.

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these symbols repeatedly during the contemplation process, without depending on the predefined meanings, because the masonic life is a place where thought, contemplation and the search for meaning continue forever. is the journey.

The concept of symbolism relates to the relative nature of knowledge. Symbolism allows for reflection, which may be used to conjure the universal principles that govern everything, as well as one's own personal history and the history of their society. In the same way that Socrates approached the problem, symbolists contend that human aim knowledge may be reached via the use of subjective knowledge. The philosophy of Socrates states that "Knowing oneself is the way to know the cosmos and God." [Citation needed] Freemasons, who internalized this adage, make it a point to use evidence while trying to get a better understanding of the link between ideas and wants, as well as any dogmatic components. (Beresniak, 2000. p. 10)

Based on the assumption that every human being is a micro-universe, it is necessary to accept the fact that it is not the right approach to limit humans to a specific set of meanings and thoughts, and that free thinking and the search for new meanings are an ontological outcome of humans.

In the section where we mentioned the operative period of Freemasonry, we said that various elements belonging to this period were also carried over to the speculative period of Freemasonry. At this point, we can say that the items mentioned are the main materials used in the construction work. ³¹The new and abstract meanings ascribed to tools such as a stonemason's pencil, hammer, compass, miter and ruler shape the Masonic world.

"Tools are, in my opinion, the most basic and real objects we have. All of them express a value, and these values have equivalents in both the inner and outer worlds, and they mean the same. Therefore, tools are the bond we set up with life, and they turn Freemasonry and its ideals into a concrete unity that expresses a lifestyle with a direct claim to life." (Han, 2021, p. 94)

Based on the expressions in the paragraph, we can clearly say that the masons see the tools of construction called tools as guides, which they strengthen by constantly attributing new meanings to transform their spirit world, behavior patterns and lifestyles (in a positive sense). Other remarkable elements of Masonic studies are the holy books on the pulpit in the middle of the

³¹Toolbox is a plural word, but it is often misused as Toolboxes.

temple. Sacred books are transcendent values that every freemason who has entered brotherhood respects, called the light of truth and believed to form the theoretical basis of the relationship between the Great Architect of the Universe and humanity. These three books, which are located on the pulpit with the miter and compass, are under the responsibility of the brother appointed as the Holy Book Trustees,³² although it is not a necessity for masons to be monotheists as long as they believe in a transcendent supreme creator, the combination of the holy books (the light of the truth) and the square and compass. The supreme value system that appeared because of this system forms the basis of both Masonic studies and Masonic philosophy. The holy books, which are an inseparable part of the ideal temple in regular freemasonry, preserve their existence today as they were yesterday, as concrete evidence against accusations such as "enemy of religion, atheism" developed against freemasonry. Perhaps, taking a stand against bigotry, which appeared because of the degeneration of the divine will and values through individuals and institutions and becoming a tool of domination over societies, is deliberately presented as hostility to religion or atheism by the mobs who monopolize divine authority.

7. **Written Principles of Freemasonry: The Anderson Code**

Today, we can say that the basic text declaring the basic principles of speculative (especially Nizami) Freemasonry is the Anderson Regulations. The Anderson Code was written between 1718 and 1723 by James Anderson, who, as the name suggests, was a freemason. We mentioned that in 1717 the four lodges in England came together to form the United Grand Lodge of England (UGLE). Anderson, who wrote the regulation at the request of Grand Master George Payne, concluded this work with the contributions of a committee set up by Masons. The ratification and declaration of the regulation took place on January 14, 1723.

The Anderson Regulation has undergone several rounds of revision and adjustment throughout the course of its existence, all of which are conducted in line with the zeitgeist and the requirements of the human mind. Even though it was written by James Anderson and attributed to a single person under the name of the Anderson Regulations, this regulation is a common product of the human

³²believes in one god

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mind, and it is possible to say that many masons contributed either directly or indirectly to the formation of the intellectual components that make up this regulation. For instance, George Payne was the one who penned a part of the legislation as well as the statute that governs the statute. Anthony Sayer, Jean Théophile Desaguliers, John Duc de Montagu, Jouhn Beal, and Phillippe Names such as Duc de Wharton also made significant contributions to the legislation. From this vantage point, it is incontestable that it has gone through several transformations throughout the course of time. The laws of nature and the character of man both need the ever-present presence of change in the world. The rule addresses a wide variety of concerns, some of which are more specific than others. These concerns range from the way the work of freemasonry should be conducted to the belief system of masons. Although there are primarily three distinct versions dated 1723, 1738, and 1815, the rule has also undergone some minor alterations in new editions with shorter intervals between them. These new editions have been published more recently. These alterations concern not only the contents of the book but also its outward appearance and qualities. It is fair to say that the most significant adjustment to the rule was made to the section under "God and Faith."

Below is how Anderson dealt with "God and Faith" in the latest edition of the Code. Although the framework of the concept of belief was drawn in time with the monotheistic religions, it was rearranged because of objections and believing in the existence of a transcendent creative power was accepted as a qualification that meets the belief condition in Freemasonry.

"A Mason, by virtue of his privilege, must follow the moral law, and if he has a good grasp of art, he will never be a foolish GODS nor an unbelieving RELIGIOUS. " [Citation needed] "A Mason, by virtue of his privilege, must obey the moral law. However, in ancient times, members of the Masonic fraternity had to adhere to the religion of the country or nation in which they lived. It is necessary today for everyone to respect their own right to an opinion and to subscribe to one of the faiths that are universally acknowledged as valid. In other words, to become a Freemason, a person must be a decent and virtuous person, in addition to being a man of respect and honor, regardless of what sect or creed they choose to adhere to, in addition to holding whatever title and position they have. Therefore, Freemasonry becomes the Center of Unity, and regardless of the

distances that exist between individuals, Freemasonry becomes a way by which genuine friendship may bring people together. (Şenkut, 2017, p. 24)

8. Rites as a Rating System

Freemasonry was described as a brotherhood system that incorporates personal evolutionary processes earlier in this article. If we acknowledge that the process of human evolution is a slow one (which is the rule of nature), then we can say that this process runs in two distinct ways. The first of the processes occurs in human existence under natural settings arbitrarily and independently of any technique, which means that it is not dependent on this process. This journey, which starts in the womb of the mother and continues until the time when the soul and the body are no longer connected to one another, continues until death. A person's subjective experiences, blunders, acts of kindness, or conclusions drawn from the ties he keeps with other people all contribute to the individual's involuntary and uncontrolled growth. The systematic method of evolution is yet another approach to evolution. The academic process that a person undertakes from the time that they reach mental competence, by selecting one of the initiatory pathways and thereby satisfying the conditions of that path, may be considered as a sort of systematic evolution. This is because we can offer an example of systematic development.

All the labor that is done within Freemasonry is organized around these three symbolic degrees, which are referred to as apprentice, journeyman, and master, respectively. Contrary to the common misunderstanding, it is correct to argue that freemasonry forms of three degrees when considered in this setting.

So, where do the many systems that have more than three degrees and are named "Rit" stand in the study of Freemasonry?

"As we can see, the idea of ritual is used in Freemasonry with two distinct connotations, both of which are connected to one another. The first interpretation refers to the unbroken nature of a ceremonial system. The levels of participation in this ritual may range from apprentice to journeyman to master, or there may be more levels. If a rite has degrees other than apprentice,

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journeyman, and master, it is essential that they be structured outside the body of the grand lodge. This means that the concept of rite is defined as "the initiatic system that receives its members from Freemasons at the master's degree and has a unique number and content of degrees." We will discuss the reasons for this in the following sections. It brings us to the second meaning that we can convey.

The globe is home to a wide variety of rituals, each of which varies in terms of the number of participants and the amount of material involved. One such example is the Schroder Rite, which consists of only the apprentice, journeyman, and master degrees. Other examples include the 7-degree French Rite, the 8-degree Rectified Scotch Rite, the 10-degree Swedish Rite, the 13-degree York Rite, the 33-degree Old and Accepted Scotch Rite, and the 99-degree Memphis-Misraim. Rite is able to be bestowed." (Sanver, 2019, p. 23) In this context, we can conclude that rites are a degree of philosophical study, that they should be accepted as study systems that appeared in different geographies and times, have different methods and give different symbolic titles to masons who have received the relevant degree. Although each rite system has its own rituals and motifs, we can underline that not all of them exist in all geographies.

9. Conclusion

"As we can see, the term of rite is used in Freemasonry with two distinct connotations that are yet connected to one another. The first interpretation refers to the unbroken nature of a certain ceremonial system. This initiation procedure might have as little as three levels—apprentice, journeyman, and master—or it could have more than three levels. If a rite has degrees other than apprentice, journeyman, and master, it is essential that they be structured outside the body of the grand lodge. This means that the concept of rite is defined as "the initiatic system that receives its members from Freemasons at the master's degree and has a unique number and content of degrees." We will discuss the reasons for this in the sections that follow. It brings us to a second interpretation that is open to us.

The globe is home to a wide variety of rituals, each of which varies in terms of the number of participants and the amount of substance that is included. Examples of these include the Schroder Rite, which only confers the degrees of apprentice, journeyman, and master; the 7-degree French Rite; the 8-degree Rectified Scotch Rite; the 10-degree Swedish Rite; the 13-degree York Rite; the 33-degree Old and Accepted Scotch Rite; and the 99-degree Memphis-Misraim. Riti is available to be bestowed." (Sanver, 2019, p. 23)

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